

INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY INTO THE COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING APPROACH TO ENHANCE EFFECTS OF ENGLISH GRAMMAR TEACHING: A CRITICAL REVIEW AND APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

It is a common belief that English grammar is an integral part of the English acquisition as a foreign language (EFL). A high level of proficiency in English grammar enables students to express themselves accurately and fluently in the use of English in both classrooms and real-life social contexts. Unfortunately, English grammar lessons are often thought by many students to be difficult and boring. Therefore, how to teach English grammar effectively is an issue that requires due attention from the teacher. This paper mainly discusses how to enhance the effectiveness of an English grammar lesson by integrating technology into the communicative language teaching approach (CLT approach). In particular, the paper presents the crucial concepts of the methods to teach English grammar lessons communicatively, and the conceptual framework for integrating technology into the CLT approach therefrom practical activities are respectively illustrated to teach an English grammar lesson. Furthermore, this paper reviews suggestions for the effective integration of technology in the contexts of English learning and teaching.

Keywords: communicative language teaching, English grammar teaching, integrating technology, student motivations.

1 INTRODUCTION

English grammar is widely considered an important part of the communicative ability of English. However, to many EFL students, English grammar lessons are less attractive than other aspects of English learning because these lessons are still taught in the formats of traditional practice isolated from contextual meanings. In addition, due to the mixed-levels in EFL classrooms and large-size classes, some of the students may obtain fewer benefits from the lessons than others. In other aspects, the effectiveness of an English grammar lesson also depends on the students' interests and motivations. It is commonly accepted that students are more motivated and overcome difficulties to achieve the expectations of learning English when having strong motivations. Therefore, the teachers need to focus on raising the students' motivations when teaching English and especially in English grammar lessons.

The number of people learning English has dramatically increased because of the reinforcing requirements of effective English communication in many fields. This has led the teachers to an important change in the English language teaching methods. In this situation, the teachers need to help their students foster the communicative competence in real-life situations. The communicative

language teaching approach seems to be an appropriate choice for the new purpose of English learning (learning to communicate) from students. As mentioned by Richards (2006), activities in CLT wish to integrate the grammar competence into the English communicative competence in order to develop the students' proficiency in English.

Today's English learning and teaching tools, Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) is a system which helps students to practise four-English skills effectively. Alternatively, the smartphone, the most popular personal device, which has many useful technical functions for the learning and teaching of English. Both teachers and students can use smartphones to download various kinds of English materials on the Internet easily. The computer and smartphone assistants provide the students a stress-free environment and make them more responsible for their learning. As mentioned by Sharma & Barret (2007), students are able to access the Internet from everywhere (home, office, or even coffee shops) to review instructional materials that they have not understood when studying in the class.

Over past decades, much of the research dealing with technology in the English language teaching has emphasized its impact on students' engagement with academic studies. However, integrating technology into the communicative language teaching approach to improve the effects of English grammar lessons in the contexts of English language teaching in Vietnam, perhaps, is the new trend that needs to be evaluated fully. To fill the research gap, an overview of the teaching English grammar methods, theoretical reviews and practical illustrations on how to integrate technology into the communicative language teaching approach to teach English grammar, are respectively given in the following sections.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Why to teach English grammar in the communicative language teaching approach

According to Richards (2006), the CLT approach has fundamentally changed the formats of English grammar lessons from focusing mainly on grammatical structures and traditional practice through controlled activities (especially learning by heart conversations and grammatical structures) into the application of interactive activities (including group-work and pair-work activities, role plays, or project-based activities). Similarly, Harmer (2015) argues that activities in CLT typically involve students in real or realistic communication.

In a study conducted in the Vietnamese contexts, Pham and Nguyen (2014) conclude that teaching English grammar in the CLT approach not only helps students enhance the grammar competence and use it effectively in communication (at least in oral production) but also increase the students' motivations in English grammar learning. In another experimental study, Nguyen and Nguyen (2004) find out that the group of students in the communicative English grammar class with many interactive activities are more interested in learning, compared to the other groups of students in the grammar-translation class with traditional controlled activities. In conclusion, the CLT approach makes English grammar lessons more interactive and attractive and provides students opportunities to use the English grammar structures in contextual meanings.

How to teach English grammar in the communicative language teaching approach

A brief history of the English grammar teaching methodology

In the history of English language teaching to the students of English as a foreign language, Grammar Translation Methods (GTM) is the first method used for teaching the English language. In

this method, the teacher explains English grammar structures deductively in the mother language and students learn by heart these structures and practise through translation exercises.

Damaris and Ginneth (2013) argue that the deductive explanation of English grammar encourages a teacher-centered classroom, prevents students from producing their own language the lesson, and even reduces learning motivations from some students, especially younger ones. Due to the disadvantages of GTM methods, English grammar is inductively taught in the Direct Method. To more specially, English grammar structures are taught through examples, demonstrations, objects, or pictures. The teacher focuses on correcting both pronunciation and grammar. Students are more proactive in the learning process, rather than being simply passive in term of the acquisition of grammar.

In terms of structure-based approach, the Audiolingual Method, which wishes students to communicate in English – the target language (L2) through memorization of grammatical structures and word sounds. Based on heavy and regular drills of the English grammatical patterns, as examined by Harmer (2015), students could overcome the habits of their native language and form good habits of the English use inside and outside classrooms.

The rapid growth of the demand for good communication in English has also required significant changes in English grammar teaching methodology. As commented by Nunan (2004), an outstanding distinction between “*knowing that*” and “*knowing how*” is a distinction between knowing and being able to form grammatical rules and being able to use this grammatical knowledge to communicate effectively. Since the CLT approach started popularly in the early 1970s (the CLT-modern period), it has been globally applied in most classrooms of English as a foreign language in order to meet the new aforementioned purpose from many students. As reported by Larsen-Freeman & Anderson (2011), the main purpose of applying the communicative language teaching approach is for students broadly to achieve communicative competence. In short, grammatical competence is thought to be less important than communicative competence in the CLT-modern period.

In the CLT post-modern period (from the late 1990s to the present), English grammar is considered an integral part of communicative competence. According to Richards (2006), English grammar is not taught in isolation but often arises out of a communicative task, and lessons are implemented in both the inductive and deductive approaches.

Figure 1 below shortly summarizes the changes in English grammar methods following the history of English language teaching methodology.

How to teach English grammar in the communicative language teaching approach

As proposed by Li & Song (2007), the relationship between English grammatical competence and English communicative competence is the relationship between “absorbing” and “practising”. This means that grammatical knowledge of English is from the practice of English. To do so successfully, students are firstly required to participate in the reactive activities of listening and reading skills to induce and discover the formation and function of English grammar. Concurrently, students and the teacher jointly outline what are the rules of English grammar after practice activities of the four-English skills.

Instead of introducing English grammar deductively, teachers should firstly give examples of the English grammar structure in the form of pictures, drawings or objects, and explain to students through those examples (the inductive approach). As commented by Doff (1998), showing visuals

not only helps students use English grammar structures appropriately in in-outside classrooms through comprehensively contextual understandings but also keeps the students' attention in the teaching process.

In order to teach students to use the adjectives of people descriptions (such as *tall, short, thin, fat, blond, brown, curly, or straight*) practically, Sandra and Gómez (2014) suggest that the teacher firstly explains the meanings of these adjectives by the pictures of different people and demonstrates how to pronounce them. Afterwards, a student describes a classmate in the class, whereas others guess who is described. In this situation, the English grammar is used within an actual communicative context, where the real information is given and it is not predictable (Richards, 2006).

Figure 1: The brief history of English Grammar Teaching Methods

A critical overview of integrating technology into the communicative language teaching approach to enhance the effects of English grammar teaching

Despite its contributions, the principles of the CLT approach are not always simple to put into practice in various local situations. Due to mixed-level and unmotivated students and large-size classes, certainly, teachers have some problems in utilizing the CLT approach in English grammar teaching. In most EFL contexts including Vietnam, students only use English inside the class, and they do not have more opportunities to practice English outside the class. Using numerous activities and making the lessons lively seem to be effective methods for teachers to motivate

students in learning English. Liu (2015) proposes that students are more autonomous in learning when they are immersed in a variety of interesting activities both inside and outside the class.

Obviously, the application of technology in the English language teaching provides a student-centered learning environment. Based on a CALL system, the teacher guides students on how to use a variety of online resources and instructional materials from anywhere and at any time. Furthermore, a smartphone can be used effectively in teaching and learning English as a foreign language wherever and whenever possible. As Richards (2014) observed, students can use available English language learning apps and watch videos in English (following with subtitles if necessary) on the Internet with their smartphones while waiting for public transports.

In consideration of the foregoing, integrating technology into the communicative language teaching approach seems to be an effective solution to problems of English grammar teaching. This attempt wishes to draw a critical relation between technology-assisted education and the communicative language teaching approach in English learning and teaching in this decade influenced strongly by Industry 4.0. This is also hoping for important changes in English teaching methods in the Vietnamese contexts, while the current methods and classroom practices are outdated, relying almost entirely on stringent teacher-centered pedagogical techniques and rote learning (Nguyen, L.V., 2010).

Figure 2 below generally illustrates the conceptual framework for integrating Technology into the communicative language teaching approach to teaching English Grammar effectively.

Figure 2: The conceptual framework for integrating technology into the communicative language teaching approach to teaching English grammar

3 PROCEDURE

To illustrate how to integrate technology into the communicative language teaching approach to enhance the effects of English grammar teaching, the practical activities of a particular lesson are described below. Through participating in interactive activities in CLT inside the class, the students inductively discover the new English grammar rules, concurrently they have more opportunities for communication in English while working in groups to complete a video project outside the class. The following sections are about the background information of the lesson and how the practical activities of its being used in the classrooms.

Background information

Learning objective: The lesson is intended for students to reflect on how to use the reported speech in practice the four-English skills, practise and develop group working skills

Student level: The lesson is best used for the students of the pre-intermediate English language, corresponding the Common European Framework of Reference for languages (CEFR). The lesson should take place after students have had exposure to the basic structure of the English verb tenses including, the present simple and the past simple

Class size: The lesson can be implemented in large-sized classes from 30 to 40 students

Organization: individual, groups, and the whole class

Language focus: The reported speech, the relative pronoun

Alternatives: The present simple and the past simple of English verb tenses

Teaching method: Communicative language teaching (Richards, 2006), including such main activities as Task-completion, Opinion-sharing, Information-transfer, Roleplays, or Project-based, engaged in individuals, groups, or the whole class

Technology equipment: smartphones, iPods, laptops, tablet PCs, social networks, and apps for teaching and learning English (**Appendix A**)

The conduction of practical activities in English classrooms

The lesson template is particularly implemented in the following activities:

Activity 1: The teacher demonstrates a real-life conversation containing the direct and reported speech.

Hung: *Hey, Tuan! What did John say to you yesterday?*

Tuan: *Well, he said "I often play tennis with my friends"*

Hung: *"He said that he often played tennis with his friends!" Really?*

Tuan: *Yes, it is.*

The contextual descriptions of the conversation

In an English classroom, Tuan and Hung are talking about their friend, John from England. In the conversation, Tuan is retelling what John talked to him on the telephone yesterday.

Activity 2: The teacher requires some pairs of the students to make roleplays of the aforementioned conversation in front of the class. In order to create authentic-video folders which can be used in the next lessons, the teacher can record the students' roleplays by a smartphone. Following this, some of the students are asked to read the direct and reported speech in the conversation (**Table 1**) aloud.

Table 1: The examples of the direct and reported speech in the conversation

	Introduction	Direct speech	Reported speech
Example	He said:	"I often play tennis with my friends."	He said that he often played tennis with his friends.
Tense	<i>Past simple</i>	<i>Present simple</i>	<i>Past simple</i>

Activity 3: The teacher divides the students into groups of five to seven students. After discussion in groups, the students guess what the rules are from the examples described above, and explain them to other students in front of the class.

Activity 4: Generally, the teacher explains how to change the direct speech into the reported speech to the students.

Activity 5: In the practical time, the students write some direct sentences in the present simple tense. After that, the students are asked to exchange their direct sentences together, correct errors if necessary, and change the formats of these sentences from direct sentences to reported sentences.

Activity 6: The teacher designs more practical tasks in working pairs or groups (making conversations, making small talks, or writing a short paragraph) that provide the students opportunities for interactive communication in English. This activity helps the students better prepare for their projects (making a video about daily activities) in the **Activity 7**. For example, the students make conversations about daily activities with suggested questions below:

- *What time do you often get up?*
- *When do you often start and finish lessons at school?*
- *What do you often do after school?*
- *How often do you go to the cinema?*

Activity 7: To practise English outside the classrooms, the students are required to make a video about the topic “*Talking about your daily activities*” (project-based learning). The teacher explains the task clearly to the students so that they are going to work in a group and make a video which is between 10 and 15-minute long. In this video, the students will have applied the new grammatical rules what they learned in the lesson, including adverbs of frequency, the basic structure of the English verb tenses – the present simple and the past simple, and relative pronouns. Most importantly, all of the students in each group will have participated in this video.

To effectively make a video, the teacher firstly guides the students how to find ideas for their videos, or how to use some special functions namely text-to-speech programs creations or movie/TV scripts creations at some websites on the Internet (**Appendix A**).

After completing their videos, the students will have uploaded their videos on an online classroom-account, created by the teacher at the website <https://classroom.google.com> (this website enables the teacher to establish deadlines and manage the task completion of the students effectively, and the students can comment on their tasks or other students’ tasks). Concurrently, the students evaluate the videos, following the video assessment rubric – the students’ version (Appendix B). In addition to the evaluations from students, the teacher examines the students’ projects following the video assessment rubric – the teacher’s version (Appendix C). This requires the students to seriously participate in the learning projects.

Based on what evaluated above, the groups of the students having the most interesting videos are asked to make presentations about their videos in the class. Finally, the teacher requires the students to change the direct speech in these videos into the reported speech.

4 DISCUSSION

Table 2 below provides briefly a summary of the consistency between practical activities in the lesson and the principle of the English language teaching methodology (ELT).

Table 2: The compare-contrasted analysis between the lesson conductions and the English language teaching methodology theory

Analytical Categories	Principles
1. The teacher distributes conservation containing a target grammar structure.	➤ Whenever possible, the teacher should use learning materials related to real contexts (<i>authentic language</i>) in the language teaching.
2. Students make roleplays in pair work in front of the class.	➤ Students should be given an opportunity to practise the language as much as possible in the class. The social context of the communicative event is essential in giving meaning to the utterances.
3. The students are asked to work in groups and write their own indirect speech.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Working in groups enables students to be confident to try out whatever language they know, or think they know, without fear of being wrong or of being corrected in front of the class; ➤ Communicative interaction encourages cooperative relationships among students; ➤ It gives students an opportunity to work on negotiating meanings.
4. The teacher asks students to correct errors together (peer correction).	➤ This enables students to increase awareness of self-corrections in a comfortable way. Students can also learn from others.
5. Based on observations, students guess what the rule is from examples and explain it to others in the class.	➤ English grammar should be taught inductively. Students should be more active in the learning process (student-centered approach with learning by doing).
6. The teacher finally explains and outlines the rule to students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The teacher plays the roles of facilitators in the teaching process; ➤ The teacher provides the grammar knowing accuracy for students.
7. Afterwards, the teacher encourages students to do more hands-on activities (making conservations or small talks) after acquiring the new grammar structures.	➤ The teacher creates a linguistic environment to build awareness of language use in actual situations from students.

Analytical Categories	Principles
8. Students do video-projects in small groups out of the class.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ This creates the linguistic environment for students to practise English skills out of the class based on the advantages of technology; ➤ This provides opportunities to practice interactional skills, critical thinking skills, or communicative skills for students.
9. Students choose ideas for the video and give feedback and evaluate videos together through social networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Students, with free choices what they really like doing, will be more motivated in learning and engage in and out of class. ➤ Students can also learn from others with peer evaluations.
10. The teacher asks students to change direct speech in the video records into reported speech.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The grammar and vocabulary need to be practised regularly and engaged in the function and situational contexts.

Today’s students, the use of modern personal devices is mostly an integral part of their daily life. As a result, the integration of technology as described above firstly can be applied in real-life contexts, and concurrently creates more opportunities for students to use their English language resources. Amongst the advantages of this integration, students can be more interactive with others in the proposed learning tasks and activities. In a convenient way, students might comfortably give their feedback or receive comments on their speaking from others in the class. This seems to be an effective solution to encourage the unmotivated students to be more active in the learning process.

From the conductions of aforementioned practical activities, there are many benefits to English grammar teaching. Of these benefits, the use of examples to teach English grammar engages students in the purposeful use of English and concentrates on the meaning of the English structures. As suggested by Doff (1988), contextual illustrations of English grammar allow students to discover how English grammar structures were formed and engage them in practicing situations.

From the student’s positions, doing projects in groups increases the engagement between students and fosters the essential skills namely critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, communicative skills, or skills for long-life learning. Working in pairs or groups also makes students more confident in the use of English grammar – without fear of being wrong or of being corrected in front of the class. Students can correct grammar errors together (peer correction) when practising English in groups or pairs. Richards (2014) suggests that the regular use of out-of-class projects in language teaching facilitates an English immersive environment where students can transfer what is learned for an actual communicative purpose outside the class.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper contains how to integrate technology into the communicative language teaching approach to enhance the effects of English grammar teaching. The teacher needs to focus on raising the students’ motivations and engagement in the English teaching process. In EFL classrooms of mixed-level students, students of lower-level might learn from others, and students

can correct errors together (peer correction) when speaking English in groups or pairs. In order to make English grammar lessons more interactive and attractive to the students, the teacher integrates technology into the communicative language teaching approach. For students, this might be a platform to improve the four-English skills and more ready to face the challenges of Industry 4.0. However, a request for certain conditions, including the available computer and smartphone setting, fast Internet connection, secure platforms and expertise, which is extremely important to the success of any technology integration, needs to be met (Pirani, 2004, as cited by Al-Mahrooqi & Troudi, 2014). Furthermore, the teachers themselves will not be able to make the best use of technology without the help and support of others in the education system, including the teaching context of their classes, their schools, their Rectors and the relevant authorities (Lee, Pham, & Tan, 2019). The author also calls for further studies in the English grammar teaching with technology.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A

SOCIAL NETWORKS, APPS, WEBSITES SUPPORTING LEARNERS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

Social networks & Supporting websites	Language Apps for students to use on smartphones
1. Facebook, Zalo; Whatsapp, Intergarm 2. http://movies.go.com ; 3. www.youtube.com ; 4. https://classroom.google.com ; 5. www.script-o-rama.com ; 6. www.simplyscripts.com ; 7. www.research.att.com/~ttsweb/tts/demo.php 8. www.research.ibm.com/tts/coredemo.shtml	1. Duolingo – language courses; 2. HelloTalk – chat and Q&A; 3. HiNative – chat and Q&A; 4. Mindsnacks – language games; 5. Memrise – flashcards and SRS; 6. Leaf – context and idioms; 7. Lingua.ly – native reading and materials; 8. Busuu – language courses

Appendix B

VIDEO ASSESSMENT RUBRIC – STUDENTS’ VERSION

Topic: _____ **Group’s name:** _____

Examiner’s name: _____ **Leader’s name:** _____

Instructions: Evaluate each criteria below by sticking (✓) the corresponding number using the following four-point scale:

EVALUATED CATEGORIES	Needs improvement (1)	Fair (2)	Good (3)	Excellent (4)
Maintaining fewest errors or mistakes in grammar and pronunciation				
Using enough the required grammar rules				
Using enough the required lexical resources				
Having a coherent speaking				
Having the most interesting contents				
Having the most effective special functions namely text-to-speech programs creations or movie/TV scripts creations				
Overall effectiveness				

Additional comments:

Appendix C

VIDEO ASSESSMENT RUBRIC – TEACHERS’ VERSION

Topic: _____ **Group’s name:** _____

Examiner’s name: _____ **Leader’s name:** _____

Instructions: Evaluate each criteria below by sticking (✓) the corresponding number using the following four-point scale:

EVALUATED CATEGORIES	Needs improvement (1)	Fair (2)	Good (3)	Excellent (4)
Maintaining fewest errors or mistakes in grammar and pronunciation				
Using enough the required grammar rules				
Using enough the required lexical resources				
Having a coherent speaking				
Having the most interesting contents				
Having the most effective special functions namely text-to-speech programs creations or movie/TV scripts creations				
All of the group members participated in the video				
Being the earliest group uploading the video				
Overall effectiveness				

Additional comments:
